

NEW MEXICO
ANIMAL DAMAGE
CONTROL PROGRAM

SUMMARY OF PROGRAM ACTIVITIES
FISCAL YEAR 1993

United States Department of Agriculture
Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service
and
New Mexico Department of Agriculture

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE
ANIMAL AND PLANT INSPECTION SERVICE
ANIMAL DAMAGE CONTROL PROGRAM
NEW MEXICO

SUMMARY OF PROGRAM ACTIVITIES
FISCAL YEAR 1993

IN COOPERATION WITH
STATE OF NEW MEXICO

Thru

NEW MEXICO STATE UNIVERSITY-NEW MEXICO DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE

CURT MULLIS
State Director

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Albuquerque, New Mexico 87113

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NEW MEXICO ANIMAL DAMAGE CONTROL PROGRAM PERSONNEL, FY 1994

All employees are full time-permanent unless otherwise indicated.

State Office, Albuquerque

Curt Mullis	State Director	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Saidor Turman	Asst. State Dir.	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Edna Weed	Budget Analyst	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Lynda Cubra	Computer Asst.	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Patsy Baca	Accounting Tech.	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Randy French	State Office Asst.	Federal	Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Lori Glenn	State Office Asst. (Temp)		Albuquerque, Bernalillo County
Yvonne Macias	State Office Asst. (Temp)		Albuquerque, Bernalillo County

Albuquerque District

Ken Podborny	Dist. Supervisor	Federal	Corrales, Bernalillo County
Ray McCoy	Master ADC Spec.	Federal	Logan, Quay County
George Cornelius	ADC Specialist	Federal	Belen, Valencia County
Robert Fifer	ADC Specialist	State	Thoreau, Cibola/McKinley County
Jimmy Garcia	ADC Specialist	State	Roy, Harding County
Pat Jaureguiberry	ADC Specialist	State	Las Vegas, San Miguel County
Earl Jones, Jr.	ADC Specialist	Federal	Los Lunas, Valencia County
Ron Jones	ADC Specialist	State	Tucumcari, Guadalupe County
Max Martinez	ADC Specialist	Federal	Bernalillo, Sandoval County
Larry Sandoval	ADC Specialist	Federal	Encino, Torrance County
Ronald Ulibarri	ADC Specialist	Federal	Alcalde, Rio Arriba County

Las Cruces District

Alan May	Dist. Supervisor	Federal	Las Cruces, Dona Ana County
Randy Baxter	Asst. Dist. Sup.	Federal	Hurley, Grant County
Pat Duran	Clerk Typist	Federal	Las Cruces, Dona Ana County
Johnny Anglin	ADC Specialist	Federal	Cuchillo, Sierra County
Vance Anglin	ADC Specialist	Federal	Las Cruces, Dona Ana County
Darrell Cole	Student Trainee	Federal	Las Cruces, Dona Ana County
Dan Davis	ADC Specialist	Federal	Weed, Otero County
Quentin Dean	ADC Specialist	State	Pinon, Otero County
Archie Graham	ADC Specialist	State	Deming, Luna County
Mike Graves	ADC Specialist	Federal	Animas, Hidalgo County
Ty Hobbs	ADC Specialist	State	Deming, Luna County
Orland Hughes	ADC Specialist	State	Pinon, Otero County
Bobby Hughey	ADC Specialist	Federal	Reserve, Catron County
Gaston Lewis	ADC Specialist	Federal	Pinon, Otero County
Esther Nelson	Student Trainee	Federal	Las Cruces, Dona Ana County

Roswell District

Larry Killgo	Dist. Supervisor	Federal	Roswell, Chaves County
Louann Metcalf	Office Clerk (part-time)	Federal	Roswell, Chaves County
Johnnie Ballou	ADC Specialist	State	Tatum, Lea County
Max Cummings	ADC Specialist	Federal	Roswell, Chaves County
Jack Davidson Jr.	ADC Specialist	State	Corona, Lincoln County
Wayne Derrick	ADC Specialist	State	Maljamar, Lea County
Charles Fletcher	ADC Specialist	State	Hope, Eddy County
Corky Hare	ADC Specialist	State	Mayhill, Chaves County
Dean Harris	ADC Specialist	State	Malaga, Eddy County
Lane Jones	ADC Specialist	State	Roswell, Chaves County
William Landrie	ADC Specialist	Federal	Artesia, Eddy County
Dwayne Milliron	ADC Specialist	State	Ft. Sumner, DeBaca County
Greg Nunnally	ADCS Gunner	State	Roswell, Chaves County
Johnny Patterson	ADC Specialist	State	Tinnie, Lincoln County
Keith O'Neal Rea	ADC Specialist	State	Artesia, Lincoln County
Frank Sisneros	ADC Specialist	State	San Patricio, Lincoln County
Gary Stevens	ADC Specialist	Federal	Capitan, Lincoln County
Alan Theobald	Pilot	Federal	Roswell, Chaves County
Paul Wasson	ADC Specialist	State	Roswell, Chaves County

Cole, Darrell, entered on duty 01/18/93.
Glenn, Lori, temporary appointment ended on 08/31/93.
Graham, Jack, retired 10/31/92.
Hobbs, Ty, entered on duty 03/29/93.
Jones, Lane, entered on duty 12/21/92.
Macias, Yvonne, entered on duty 09/01/93.
May, Alan, entered on duty 10/04/92.
Nelson, Esther, entered on duty 02/07/93.
Wasson, Paul, retired 10/31/92.
Weed, Echa, entered on duty 11/15/92.

Table 1a. Employment and expenditures by the New Mexico ADC program, FY 1993

Reg	St	Funding Source	Funding Type	Staff Years	Breakdown of Expenditures by Resource Protected							Total	
					Agriculture				Health & Safety	Property	Natural Resources		
					Aquaculture	Livestock	Forest/Range	Crops			Wildlife		
W	NM	FEDERAL	SUPERVISORY	4.69	191	139,737	11,438	21,542	5,910	9,913	1,906	190,637	
W	NM	FEDERAL	ADMINISTRATIVE/CLERICAL	4.78	90	65,758	5,383	10,137	2,781	4,665	897	89,711	
W	NM	FEDERAL	FIELD	17.45	841	616,485	50,463	95,038	26,072	43,734	8,411	841,044	
			Subtotal	26.92	1,122	821,980	67,284	126,717	34,763	58,312	11,214	1,121,392	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	FEDERAL REIMBURSABLE									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	STATE REIMBURSABLE	0.00	30	21,990	1,800	3,390	930	1,560	300	30,000	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	COUNTY REIMBURSABLE									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	CITY REIMBURSABLE									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	ORGANIZATION REIMBURSABLE									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	INDIVIDUAL REIMBURSABLE									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	STATE TRUST FUNDS									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	COUNTY TRUST FUNDS									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	CITY TRUST FUNDS									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	ORGANIZATION TRUST FUNDS									0	
W	NM	COOPERATIVE	INDIVIDUAL TRUST FUNDS									0	
			Subtotal	0.00	30	21,990	1,800	3,390	930	1,560	300	30,000	
W	NM	OTHER	STATE FUNDS	10.11	329	243,759	18,776	35,576	10,870	16,800	3,294	329,404	
W	NM	OTHER	COUNTY FUNDS	9.46		405,652	25,296	16,557	8,279	4,139		459,923	
W	NM	OTHER	CITY FUNDS									0	
W	NM	OTHER	ORGANIZATION FUNDS	0.00		49,392					1,008	50,400	
W	NM	OTHER	INDIVIDUAL FUNDS									0	
W	NM	OTHER	FUR SALES									0	
W	NM	OTHER	REVOLVING FUNDS	0.00								0	
			Subtotal	19.57	329	698,803	44,072	52,133	19,149	20,939	4,302	839,727	
			Total	46.49	1,481	1,542,773	113,156	182,240	54,842	80,811	15,816	1,991,119	

Table 1b. Personnel employed by the New Mexico ADC program, FY 1993

Reg	State	Employment Source	Permanent Full-time		Permanent Part-time		Temporary Full-time		Temporary Part-time		Totals	
			Number of Employees	Hours Worked (Pay Status)	Number of Employees	Hours Worked (Pay Status)	Number of Employees	Hours Worked (Pay Status)	Number of Employees	Hours Worked (Pay Status)	Number of Employees	Hours Worked (Pay Status)
W	NM	FEDERAL	27	53,929	1	1,271			3	1,006	31	56,205
W	NM	NON-FEDERAL	21	40,208					1	623	22	40,831
		Total	48	94,137	1	1,271	0	0	4	1,629	53	97,036

Table 2. Number of animals taken and control methods used by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Non-Chemical Control Methods										Chemical Control Methods						Totals						
				Traps			Snares			Shooting				Denning	Other	M44	DRC-1339	Zinc Phos	Avtrol	1080	Trenquillizer	Other	Target		Non-Target	Total
				Cage	Kill	Leg-Hold	Aerial Hunt	Leg/Foot	Neck	Spot-Light	Call-Ing	Shot	* IT										** UT			
		Total		258	116	1,278	470	5	875	11	422	196	11	20	3,673	523			22			7,391	32	457	7,880	

K = Killed

F = Freed

* = IT (Intentional Take) - Animals which are listed as target species on an agreement and were the intended target of the control method.

** = UT (Unintentional Take) - Animals which are listed as target species on an agreement but were not the intended target of the control method.

Table 3. Number of animals moved or dispersed and control methods used by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Cultural Practices	Habitat Modification		Behavior Modification (Harassment)		Totals			
					Barriers	Environmental Manipulation	Nonchemical	Chemical	* IT	** UT	Nontarget	
V	NM	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL					18,450		18,450		
		Total						18,450		18,450		

* IT = (Intentional Take) - Animals which are listed as target species on an agreement and were the intended target of the control method.

** UT = (Unintentional Take) - Animals which are listed as target species on an agreement but are not the intended target of the control method.

Table 4a. Resource losses reported to the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Total Loss Value
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TREES, CHRISTMAS	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	1,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TREES, SEEDLINGS	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	16	675
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TRACES, STANDING (MIXED)	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	9	12,470
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TRACES, STANDING (MIXED)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	12	1,425
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TRACES, STANDING (MIXED)	MAMMAL	POCCHIPES	1	5,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL FORESTRY & NURSERY	TRACES, STANDING (MIXED)	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	35
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL GAME ANIMALS	BIRDS, PELICAN (ALL)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	2	18
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	COMMERCIAL GAME ANIMALS	MAMMALS, 2-KILOTIC GAMES (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	13	1,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	ALFALFA	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	17	64,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	ALFALFA	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	1	100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	ALFALFA	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	30,057
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	ALFALFA	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	250	43,300
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (FIELD)	MAMMAL	CRANES, SANDHILL	115	2,900
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (FIELD)	BIRD	PIGEONS, TRAIL (ROCK DOTS)	5	300
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (FIELD)	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	1	2,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (FIELD)	BIRD	BAYERS (ALL)	1	280
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (SWEET)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	3	1
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (SWEET)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	1	0
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, CORN (SWEET)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	1	30
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, HILLO	MAMMAL	PIGEONS, TRAIL (ROCK DOTS)	1	300
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, OATS	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	2	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, OATS	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	250
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, RYE	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	1,600
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, WHEAT	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	5	2,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, WHEAT	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	625
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, 2-(OTHER)	BIRD	BLACKBIRDS, 2-(MIXED SPECIES)	1	1,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRAINS, 2-(OTHER)	BIRD	LOWS, BARNED	1	675
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRASSES/SO	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	10	25
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRASSES/SO	MAMMAL	BARS, VICARIBITS (ALL)	1	4,600
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRASSES/SO	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	2	600
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	GRASSES/SO	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	2	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	LEGUMES, WATERMELONS	MAMMAL	COYOTES	1	80
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	PEPPERS, CHILLIES	BIRD	RACCOONS	2	950
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	PEPPERS, CHILLIES	BIRD	BLACKBIRDS, 2-(MIXED SPECIES)	2	4,225
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	PEPPERS, CHILLIES	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	5	6,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	PEPPERS, CHILLIES	BIRD	SQUIRRELS, 2-(MIXED SPECIES)	1	80
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	FRUIT, CHERRIES	MAMMAL	DOT, 2-(OTHER)	1	100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	FRUIT, CHERRIES	BIRD	SPARROWS, HOUSE/ENGLISH	1	25
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	FRUIT, CHERRIES	BIRD	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	20	1,200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	FRUIT, PEARS	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	3	1,250
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	BIRD	BAYERS (ALL)	3	100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	50	1,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	MAMMAL	BATS, PACERATS/WOODRATS (ALL)	2	150
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	2	250
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	STRAWBERRIES	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	3,475
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, APPLE	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	6	1,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, APPLE	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	150
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, CHERRY	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	2,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, PEACH	MAMMAL	POCCHIPES	1	4,100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, PEACH	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	106	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, PEACH	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	2	20
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, 2-FRUIT/NUT (OTHER)	BIRD	WOODPECKERS, 2-(OTHER)	1	20
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRICES, 2-FRUIT/NUT (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	43	8,408

Table 4a. Resource losses reported to the NRY Mexico AIC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Unit	Total Loss Value
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRUSS, 2-FRUIT/TWIG (OTHER)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	1	ln	300
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRUSS, 2-FRUIT/TWIG (OTHER)	MAMMAL	PAIRIS DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	6	ln	3,200
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	TRUSS, 2-FRUIT/TWIG (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY (ALL)	1	ln	0
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	2	ea	1,500
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	20	ea	12,350
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FAIS MINGING	12	ea	2,150
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COWHAI)	8	ea	730
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	7	ea	4,000
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	242	ea	97,711
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FAIS MINGING	8	ea	2,450
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COWHAI)	8	ea	3,570
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	1	ea	25
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COWHAI)	1	ea	200
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (ADULT)	MAMMAL	PAIRIS DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	7	ea	0
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (FOALS)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	1	ea	250
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (FOALS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	1	ea	2,500
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (FOALS)	MAMMAL	PAIRIS DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	ea	0
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (EGGS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	100	ea	300
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	BEARS, RED-TAILED	20	ea	60
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	CATS, FERAL/FAIS MINGING	3	ea	3
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	39	ea	141
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	120	ea	794
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	RINGTAILS	4	ea	80
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, CHICKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	STINKS, STRIPED	41	ea	240
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, DUCKS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	2	ea	40
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, DUCKS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	2	ea	20
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, DUCKS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	2	ea	20
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, DUCKS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	6	ea	45
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, GEESE (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	6	ea	100
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, GEESE (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	10	ea	100
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, GEESE (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	STINKS, STRIPED	18	ea	90
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, GUINEAS	BIRD	OVLS, GREAT HORNED	3	ea	10,000
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, GUINEAS	BIRD	COYOTES	5	ea	250
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, PEA	MAMMAL	COYOTES	10	ea	100
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, TURKIS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	10	ea	100
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	POUL, TURKIS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	5	ea	100
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, HEATH (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	11	ea	515
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, HEATH (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	16	ea	710
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, HEATH (KIDS)	MAMMAL	BOBATS	9	ea	480
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, HEATH (KIDS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	75	ea	2,415
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, HEATH (KIDS)	MAMMAL	PROCUPIES	27	ea	1,080
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER ADULTS)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FAIS MINGING	5	ea	225
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER ADULTS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	1	ea	40
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	RABBITS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	BEARS, MOUNTAIN	4	ea	20
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	34	ea	3,505
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BOBATS	9	ea	630
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	149	ea	12,670
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	43	ea	3,910
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	FOALS, RED	2	ea	120
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COWHAI)	14	ea	755
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	30	ea	1,550
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	6	ea	360
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	BOBATS	120	ea	30,970
V	NI	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	721	ea	41,045

Table 10. Resource losses reported to the NEV EMILCO AOC program, FY 19

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents of # Lost/Damaged	Belt	Total Loss Value
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LANDS)	MURMIL	DOGS, FEAL/TRES RANGING	28	ea	1,445
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LANDS)	MURMIL	POIDS, GRAY	2	ea	100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LANDS)	MURMIL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	53	ea	1,540
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	EGGS	MURMIL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	2	ln	24
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	FED, LIVESTOCK	BIRD	BLACKBIRDS, 3-BANDED SPECIES)	1	ln	900
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	FED, LIVESTOCK	BIRD	PIGEONS, FEAL (ROCK DOVS)	1	ln	850
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	FED, LIVESTOCK	MURMIL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	ln	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	FED, LIVESTOCK	MURMIL	RACCOONS	2	ln	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	GRAIN, STORED (NON-LIVESTOCK)	MURMIL	RAIS, MURNAI	3	ln	350
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	W (STACK/BALS)	MURMIL	BEARS, BLACK	1	ln	10
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	W (STACK/BALS)	MURMIL	WILS (WUPITI)	1	ln	675
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	OTHER	W (STACK/BALS)	MURMIL	MARLBITS, COTTONTAIL	1	ln	40
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	BIRD	CLAWS, SANDHILL	156	ec	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	2,442	ec	20,300
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	DOGS, FEAL	5	ec	1,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	15,816	ec	104,415
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	PAIRIE DOGS, WHITE-TAILED	125	ec	1,400
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	BALT, LANGRANO (ALL)	40	ec	250
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	PASTURE	MURMIL	SQUIDRIS, GROND (ALL)	115	ec	600
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	RANGELAND	MURMIL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	210	ec	1,410
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	RANGELAND	MURMIL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	9,211	ec	47,215
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	RANGELAND	MURMIL	PAIRIE DOGS, WHITE-TAILED	250	ec	2,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	RANGELAND	MURMIL	MARLBITS, COTTONTAIL	42	ec	100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	RANGE/PASTURE	RANGELAND	MURMIL	RAIS, LANGRANO (ALL)	6	ec	3,800
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN (OTHER TRANSPORTATION)	MURMIL	RICE/RATS (RED)	19	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN (OTHER TRANSPORTATION)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	2	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	BIRD	WILS, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	BIRD	WILS, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	BIRD	PIGEONS, FEAL (ROCK DOVS)	24	ln	2,500
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	BIRD	RAVENS (ALL)	2	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	BIRD	STARLINGS, ROSEBEN	6	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	BALT (ALL)	9	ln	100
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	BEARS, BLACK	2	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	CATS, FEAL/TRES RANGING	16	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	COYOTES	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	DOGS, FEAL/TRES RANGING	7	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	2	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	2	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	BICE, DEER (ALL)	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	BICE, BEAST	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	RICE/RATS (RED)	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	MARLBITS	1	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	24	ln	50
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	MARLBITS, COTTONTAIL	1	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	RAIS, MURNAI	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	BALT, PACCATS/WOOLMATS (ALL)	5	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, 2-(OTHER)	99	ln	255
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SQUIDRIS, GROND (ALL)	5	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, 2-(OTHER)	49	ln	50
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, NON-POISONOUS (OTHER)	3	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, POISONOUS (ALL)	13	ln	0
V	NE	HEALTH & SAFETY	HUMAN HEALTH & SAFETY	HEALTH & SAFETY, HUMAN 2-(GENERAL)	MURMIL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	1	ln	0

Table 4a. Resource losses reported to the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Bait	Total Loss Value
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	FORESTRY (NATL. RESC)	TREES, SEEDLINGS	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	1	1a	200
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	FORESTRY (NATL. RESC)	TREES, SEEDLINGS	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	1	1a	100
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	FORESTRY (NATL. RESC)	TREES, STANDING	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	4	1a	1,000
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	FORESTRY (NATL. RESC)	TREES, STANDING	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	4	1a	21,000
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	FORESTRY (NATL. RESC)	TREES, STANDING	MAMMAL	POCIPURES	15	1a	100
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	WILDLIFE	MAMMALS, OVER, BOLS	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	3	ea	4,500
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	WILDLIFE	MAMMALS, ELK (VALPITI)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	2	ea	1,000
Y	NI	NATURAL RESOURCE	WILDLIFE	MAMMALS, PRONGHORN (ANTELOPE)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	3	ea	600
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	7	ea	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FAKE BARKING	2	ea	20
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	POISS, GRAY	2	ea	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	1	ea	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	7	ea	148
Y	NI	PROPERTY	ANIMAL	PETS (COMPANION & HOBBY ANIMALS)	MAMMAL	SQUIBBELS, GROUP (ALL)	1	ea	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	AIRCRAFT	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOTE)	1	ea	5,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	EQUIPMENT & MACHINERY (OTHER)	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOTE)	1	1a	200
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	EQUIPMENT & MACHINERY (OTHER)	BIRD	STALLOWS, 2-(HIND)	1	1a	5,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	EQUIPMENT & MACHINERY (OTHER)	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	1	1a	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	EQUIPMENT & MACHINERY (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	1	1a	250
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	EQUIPMENT & MACHINERY (OTHER)	MAMMAL	PRADIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	2	1a	2,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	VEHICLES, LAND	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOTE)	1	ea	500
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	VEHICLES, LAND	MAMMAL	BATS, LONGEOD (ALL)	1	ea	30
Y	NI	PROPERTY	EQUIPMENT	VEHICRAFT	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	1	ea	150
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	BIRD	COONS (ALL)	10	1a	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	6	1a	1,435
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	14	1a	2,900
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	BURNS, JACARANTHS (ALL)	33	1a	2,690
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	BURNS, JACARANTHS (ALL)	1	1a	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	ALCOONS	1	1a	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GARDENS, VEG./FRUITS & NUTS	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	1	1a	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GOLF COURSES	MAMMAL	SQUIBBELS, GROUP (ALL)	6	1a	1,435
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GOLF COURSES	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	14	1a	2,900
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GOLF COURSES	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	1	1a	2,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GOLF COURSES	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	1	1a	300
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	GOLF COURSES	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	25	1a	1,566
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TRUSS, STANDING & SERVIS	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	31	1a	105
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TRUSS, STANDING & SERVIS	MAMMAL	BURNS, JACARANTHS (ALL)	1	1a	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TRUSS, STANDING & SERVIS	MAMMAL	SQUIBBELS, GROUP (ALL)	1	1a	10
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	283	1a	26,399
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	BURNS, JACARANTHS (ALL)	4	1a	295
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	PRADIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	20	1a	1,200
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	RABBITS, COTTONTAIL	8	1a	980
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	RABBITS, 2-(OTHER)	1	1a	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	1	1a	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	BATS, MURRAY	1	1a	10
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	12	1a	1,580
Y	NI	PROPERTY	LANDSCAPING, TURF & GARDENS	TURF AND/OR FLOWERS	MAMMAL	SQUIBBELS, GROUP (ALL)	47	1a	2,350
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	4	1a	6,810
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	PRADIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	3	1a	2,100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	1	1a	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	BATS, PACIFATS/ROBATS (ALL)	2	1a	300
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SQUIBBELS, GROUP (ALL)	4	1a	975
Y	NI	PROPERTY	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	2-LANDSCAPING (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SPOBENS, POCKET (ALL)	1	1a	20
Y	NI	PROPERTY	OTHER PROPERTY	FOOD ITEMS, HUMAN	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOTE)	1	1a	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	OTHER PROPERTY	OTHER PROPERTY	BIRD	GRACKLES (ALL)	1	1a	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	OTHER PROPERTY	OTHER PROPERTY	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOTE)	1	1a	500

Table 4a. Resource losses reported to the NYM NM100 ABC program, FY 93

Reg St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Unit	Total Loss Value
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	1	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	7	ln	56,241
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	KICS, 2-FIELD (OTHER)	1	ln	10,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	50	ln	13,935
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, LANGRHO (ALL)	1	ln	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, NEVAD	1	ln	200
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, PACIFIC/FOOTRATS (ALL)	2	ln	3,200
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	1	ln	150
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, GRAY	6	ln	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY	1	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY (ALL)	13	ln	1,240
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	ln	1,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	POI, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	500
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	PIGONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	27	ln	17,900
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	RAVENS (ALL)	1	ln	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	SPARROWS, HOUSE/ENGLISH	3	ln	1,125
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	STALLOWS, BARN	1	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	WOODPECKERS, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	25
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	CATS, FERAL/FRSE RANGING	1	ln	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	CHEMPANS (ALL)	2	ln	40
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	1	ln	10
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	KICS, BOSS	1	ln	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	PAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	ln	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, NEVAD	2	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	4	ln	107
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY (ALL)	2	ln	520
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	FLOCKERS (ALL)	3	ln	4,300
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	PIGONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	9	ln	3,175
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	SPARROWS, HOUSE/ENGLISH	2	ln	550
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	STALLOWS, EUROPEAN	4	ln	655
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	SHALLOWS, BARN	1	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	BIRD	WOODPECKERS, 2-(OTHER)	8	ln	5,535
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS (ALL)	4	ln	185
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	CATS, FERAL/FRSE RANGING	2	ln	10
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	CHEMPANS (ALL)	2	ln	10
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FRSE RANGING	4	ln	128
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	5	ln	250
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	KICS, BEER (ALL)	1	ln	0
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	KICS, BOSS	4	ln	50
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	PROCPINES	1	ln	20
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	1	ln	500
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, LANGRHO (ALL)	2	ln	75
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, PACIFIC/FOOTRATS (ALL)	2	ln	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	21	ln	454
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY	4	ln	70
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY (ALL)	37	ln	2,195
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	100
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	MUSKETS	1	ln	1,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	6	ln	1,950
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	COYOTES, POCKET (ALL)	4	ln	475
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	MUSKETS, 2-(OTHER)	1	ln	200
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	RATS, LANGRHO (ALL)	1	ln	15,000
Y	NI	PROPERTY	PROPERTY (GENERAL)	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY (ALL)	2	ln	1,125

Table 4a. Resource losses reported to the NEW MEXICO ADC Program, FY 93

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Unit	Total Loss Value
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	IRRIGATION /DRAINAGE	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	34	ln	9,866
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	IRRIGATION /DRAINAGE	MAMMAL	GOPIENS, POCKET (ALL)	24	ln	14,498
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	IRRIGATION /DRAINAGE	MAMMAL	PRairie DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	10	ln	4,750
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	IRRIGATION /DRAINAGE	MAMMAL	RATS, PACERATS/MOORATS (ALL)	1	ln	30
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	IRRIGATION /DRAINAGE	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	5	ln	3,799
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	ROADS/BRIDGES	BIRD	PIGDEWS, FEAL (ROCK DOWS)	1	ln	4,000
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	ROADS/BRIDGES	MAMMAL	BADGERS	1	ln	500
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	ROADS/BRIDGES	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	3	ln	4,000
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	ROADS/BRIDGES	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	1	ln	105
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	UTILITIES, ELECTRICAL	BIRD	PIGDEWS, FEAL (ROCK DOWS)	1	ln	700
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	UTILITIES, ELECTRICAL	BIRD	BEAVERS (ALL)	2	ln	3,500
V	NE	PROPERTY	STRUCTURES	UTILITIES, 2-(OTHER)	BIRD	STABLING, EUROPEAN	1	ln	10
Total									954,753

Table 4b. Resource losses reported to the NEW MEXICO ADC program, Supplement Year 92

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/damaged	Unit	Total Loss Value
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	MELONS, 2-(OTHER)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	50	lb	25
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FIELD CROPS	MELONS, 2-(OTHER)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	10	lb	13
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	MAMMAL	POIS, GRAY	5	lb	7
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	NUTS, PECANS	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	15	lb	35
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	FRUITS & NUTS	FRUITS, APPLE	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	5	ea	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	5	ea	1,600
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	52	ea	24,125
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FYRAL/FYRS RANGING	9	ea	3,700
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (ADULT)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	12	ea	9,100
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	1	ea	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	BIRD	HAWKS (ALL)	2	ea	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	21	ea	11,120
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	2	ea	1,000
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	2,499	ea	1,113,417
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FYRAL/FYRS RANGING	73	ea	30,350
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	104	ea	51,020
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	CATTLE (CALVES)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	1	ea	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (FOLLS)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	4	ea	1,550
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	EQUINE, HORSES (FOLLS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	6	ea	30
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (GUS)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FYRAL/FYRS RANGING	16	ea	35
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (GUS)	MAMMAL	HAWKS, 2-(OTHER)	10	ea	37
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (GUS)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	46	ea	244
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	246	ea	190
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	POIS, GRAY	10	ea	20
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	POIS, KIT	20	ea	60
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	22	ea	45
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	WINGTAILS	10	ea	30
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	10	ea	30
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	10	ea	45
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	19	ea	214
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GECKENS (OTHER)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	32	ea	282
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GUNNELS	MAMMAL	POIS, KIT	10	ea	50
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GUNNELS	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	10	ea	50
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, GUNNELS	MAMMAL	WINGTAILS	10	ea	50
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, FA	BIRD	SKUNKS, STRIPED	2	ea	70
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, FA	MAMMAL	COYOTES	37	ea	1,925
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, FA	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	16	ea	925
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, TURKENS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	34	ea	350
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, TURKENS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	7	ea	70
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, TURKENS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	3	ea	30
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	FOWL, TURKENS (DOMESTIC)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	7	ea	315
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	6	ea	330
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	222	ea	9,440
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (ADULT)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FYRAL/FYRS RANGING	22	ea	1,060
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (ADULT)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COEUR)	39	ea	1,935
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (KIDS)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	95	ea	3,750
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (KIDS)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	230	ea	8,325
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (KIDS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	260	ea	8,130
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (KIDS)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FYRAL/FYRS RANGING	30	ea	1,300
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, MEHAIR (KIDS)	MAMMAL	POIS, GRAY	18	ea	510
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER ADULTS)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	14	ea	900
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER ADULTS)	MAMMAL	COYOTES	5	ea	245

Table 4b. Resource losses reported to the NEW MEXICO ADC program, Supplement Year 92

Reg	St	Resource Category	Resource Subcategory	Resource	Species Group	Species Responsible	# Incidents or # Lost/Damaged	Unit	Total Loss Value
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER KIDS)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	29	ea	1,230
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	GOATS, 2-(OTHER KIDS)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	17	ea	2,250
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	32	ea	1,990
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	BIRD	RAVENS (ALL)	25	ea	1,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	25	ea	1,560
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	22	ea	1,015
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	3	ct	150
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	570	ea	46,130
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FRISK RANGING	97	ea	6,430
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COONIA)	429	ea	25,450
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (ADULT)	MAMMAL	EAGLES, BALD	12	ea	500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	BIRD	EAGLES, GOLDEN	1,124	ea	74,485
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	BIRD	RAVENS (ALL)	21	ea	1,253
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	3	ea	150
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	5	ct	200
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	BOBCATS	1,261	ea	59,471
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	3,391	ea	180,314
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	207	ea	9,742
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FRISK RANGING	32	ea	1,425
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	FOURS, GOAT	5	ea	295
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	FOURS, KIT	428	ea	22,500
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COONIA)	10	ea	480
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SHEEP (LAMB)	REPTILES	SNAKES, POISONOUS (ALL)	10	ea	480
V	NE	AGRICULTURE	LIVESTOCK	SWINE (PIG/LITS)	MAMMAL	COTUILS	4	ea	200
Total									1,733,088

Table 5a. Number of technical assistance projects* (personal, telephone, and written consultations) conducted by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Number of Projects by Resource Category Damaged				Total
				Agriculture	Health and Safety	Property	Natural Resource	
W	NM	BIRD	BLACKBIRDS, z-(MIXED SPECIES)	3				3
W	NM	BIRD	CRANES, SANDHILL	24				24
W	NM	BIRD	CROWS (ALL)			1		1
W	NM	BIRD	DOVE, zz-(OTHER)	1				1
W	NM	BIRD	FLICKERS (ALL)			2		2
W	NM	BIRD	GRACKLES (ALL)			1		1
W	NM	BIRD	HAWKS, RED-TAILED	1				1
W	NM	BIRD	HAWKS, z-(OTHER)		1			1
W	NM	BIRD	LARKS, HORNED	1				1
W	NM	BIRD	OWLS, z-(OTHER)		1			1
W	NM	BIRD	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	1	10	25		36
W	NM	BIRD	RAVENS (ALL)	3	2	3		8
W	NM	BIRD	SPARROWS, HOUSE/ENGLISH	1		4		5
W	NM	BIRD	STARLINGS, EUROPEAN		4	4		8
W	NM	BIRD	SWALLOWS, BARN			1		1
W	NM	BIRD	SWALLOWS, z-(MIXED)			1		1
W	NM	BIRD	WOODPECKERS, z-(OTHER)	1		9		10
W	NM	MAMMAL	BATS (ALL)		8	4		12
W	NM	MAMMAL	BEARS, BLACK	3	1	1		5
W	NM	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	1		4		5
W	NM	MAMMAL	CATS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	1	16	2		19
W	NM	MAMMAL	CHIPMUNKS (ALL)			4		4
W	NM	MAMMAL	COYOTES	7	2	5		14
W	NM	MAMMAL	DEER, MULE			1		1
W	NM	MAMMAL	DOGS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	4	6	6		16
W	NM	MAMMAL	ELKS (WAPITI)	1				1
W	NM	MAMMAL	FOXES, GRAY			1		1
W	NM	MAMMAL	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	262	2	330	5	599
W	NM	MAMMAL	HARES, JACKRABBITS (ALL)	1		6		7
W	NM	MAMMAL	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COUGAR)		2	1	1	4
W	NM	MAMMAL	MICE, DEER (ALL)		3	1		4
W	NM	MAMMAL	MICE, HOUSE		3	6		9
W	NM	MAMMAL	MICE/RATS (MIX)		4			4
W	NM	MAMMAL	MUSKRATS, z-(OTHER)			1		1
W	NM	MAMMAL	PORCUPINES			1	1	2
W	NM	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	348	10	47		405
W	NM	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, WHITE-TAILED	4				4
W	NM	MAMMAL	RABBITS, COTTONTAIL	1	1	5		7
W	NM	MAMMAL	RABBITS, z-(OTHER)			1		1
W	NM	MAMMAL	RACCOONS	7	2	3		12
W	NM	MAMMAL	RATS, KANGAROO (ALL)	4		3		7
W	NM	MAMMAL	RATS, NORWAY		4	4		8
W	NM	MAMMAL	RATS, PACKRATS/WOODRATS (ALL)	1	2	7		10
W	NM	MAMMAL	RINGTAILS	1		1		2
W	NM	MAMMAL	SKUNKS, STRIPED	6	63	42		111
W	NM	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GRAY			4		4
W	NM	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	12	45	115		172
W	NM	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, z-(OTHER)			1		1
W	NM	REPTILE	SNAKES, NON-POISONOUS (OTHER)		2			2
W	NM	REPTILE	SNAKES, POISONOUS (ALL)		11			11

Table 5a. Number of technical assistance projects* (personal, telephone, and written consultations) conducted by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Number of Projects by Resource Category Damaged				Total
				Agriculture	Health and Safety	Property	Natural Resource	
		Total		700	205	658	7	1,570

* The number of projects for which ADC personnel provided technical advice.

Table 5b. Number of other technical assistance projects* conducted by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Number of Projects by Project Type											Total		
				Instruct. Session	Radio/TV Appearance	Radio/TV PSA	Newspaper/Periodical	Exhibit	TA Survey	Bait Distrib.	Environ. Manipul.	Field Research Assist.	Environ. Emergency Support	Disease/Parasite Monitoring		Wildlife Damage Assessment	
W	NE	MAMMAL	BEAVERS	3													3
W	NE	MAMMAL	COYOTES	1													1
W	NE	MAMMAL	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	3	1		1				5						10
W	NE	MAMMAL	MICE/RATS (MIX)				1										1
W	NE	MAMMAL	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	5							1						6
W	NE	MAMMAL	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)								1						1
W	NE	SPECIAL	MULTPL SPP (TECH.ASST.) (SEE MTS FIELD ENDR.)	14			1	51									66
TOTAL				26	1	0	3	51	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	88

* TA projects reported in this table do not include personal, written, and telephone consultations.

Table 6. Chemical products used and supervised by the HWY MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Product Name	EPA Reg. No.	Target Species	PRIVATE LAND				PUBLIC LAND				Chemical Product Total	
					Chemical Product Amount	Unit	Acres/Premises Number	Unit*	Chemical Product Amount	Unit	Acres/Premises Number	Unit*	Amount	Unit
V	NE	AVITROL (CORN)	11649-7	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	1	oz	1	P					1	oz
V	NE	AVITROL CORN CHOPS	11649-6	SPARROWS, HOUSE/ENGLISH	2	oz	2	P					2	oz
V	NE	COMPOUND 1040 LP COLLAR	56228-22	COYOTES	53	ea	16	P					53	ea
V	NE	DIPHACIMON (HELL LABS RODENT CAKE)	12455-05	MICE, 2-FIELD (OTHER)	6	lb	6	P					6	lb
V	NE	DRC-1339 CONCENTRATE (BIRDS)	56228-10	BLACKBIRDS, 2-(MIXED SPECIES)	8	g.	8	P					8	g.
V	NE	DRC-1339 CONCENTRATE (PIGEON)	WM-810003	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	530	g.	55	P	26	g.	2	P	556	g.
V	NE	DRC-1339 CONCENTRATE (PIGEONS)	56228-28	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	11	g.	4	P					11	g.
V	NE	FUMIGANT, DETIA ROTOX AT	2548-69	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	30	ea	2	P					30	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	401	ea	57	Ac	2,247	ea	977	Ac	2,648	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	12	ea	2	P					12	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	28,165	ea	500	Ac					28,165	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	272	ea	104	P					272	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	RATS, NORWAI	60	ea	1	P					60	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	30	ea	1	Ac					30	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	367	ea	48	Ac					367	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	73	ea	4	P					73	ea
V	NE	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	24	SH	88	Ac	2	SH	15	Ac	26	SH
V	NE	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	529	ea	40	Ac					529	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (COYOTE)	56228-21	COYOTES	2	ea	2	P					2	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	323	ea	38	Ac					323	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	203	ea	75	P					203	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	98	ea	10	Ac					98	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	29	ea	2	Ac					29	ea
V	NE	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	32	ea	25	P					32	ea
V	NE	PREBAITING		PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	108	lb	26	P					108	lb
V	NE	STRICHNINE MILO (GOPHERS)	56228-19	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	62	lb	17	Ac					62	lb
V	NE	STRICHNINE MILO (GOPHERS)	56228-19	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	2	lb	1	P					2	lb
V	NE	STRICHNINE MILO (RODENTS)	56228-11	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	50	lb	48	Ac					50	lb
V	NE	STRICHNINE OATS (GOPHERS)	56228-20	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	1	lb	1	Ac					1	lb
V	NE	STRICHNINE OATS (GOPHERS)	56228-20	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	13	lb	10	P					13	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT BAIT	2393-185	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	5	lb	5	Ac					5	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT BAIT	2393-185	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	1	lb	1	P					1	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	RATS, KANGAROO (ALL)	80	lb	211	Ac					80	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	RATS, NORWAI	13	lb	7	Ac					13	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	RATS, NORWAI	1	lb	1	P					1	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	5	lb	3	Ac					5	lb
V	NE	ZINC PHOSPHIDE OATS (P.DOG)	56228-14	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	60	lb	30	Ac					60	lb

* Ac = Acres
P = Premises

Table 7. Chemical products distributed, sold, or demonstrated by the NEW MEXICO ADC program and whose use was not supervised by ADC personnel, FY 93*

Reg	St	Product Name	EPA Reg. No.	Target Species	Amount	Unit
W	NM	AVITROL (CORN)	11649-7	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	36	oz
W	NM	BRODIFACOU (TALON-G) BAIT PACK (50 g/pk)	10182-39	NICE, HOUSE	6	pk
W	NM	FUMIGANT, DETIA ROTOX AT	2548-69	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	7,600	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, DETIA ROTOX AT	2548-69	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	12,300	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	32,000	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, FUMITOXIN TABLETS	5857-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	283,407	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, GASTOXIN TABLETS	43743-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	3,100	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, GASTOXIN TABLETS	43743-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	9,500	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	13	5H
W	NM	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	16	5H
W	NM	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	4,100	ea
W	NM	FUMIGANT, PHOSTOXIN	40285-1	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	15	ea
W	NM	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	5,367	ea
W	NM	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	7,836	ea
W	NM	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	PRAIRIE DOGS, WHITE-TAILED	540	ea
W	NM	GAS CARTRIDGE (RODENT)	56228-2	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	859	ea
W	NM	NEUTROLEUM ALPHA		CATS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	48	oz
W	NM	NEUTROLEUM ALPHA		DOGS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	40	oz
W	NM	NEUTROLEUM ALPHA		RATS, NORWAY	1	oz
W	NM	NEUTROLEUM ALPHA		SKUNKS, STRIPED	240	oz
W	NM	REPELLENT, RO-PEL	45735-2	HARES, JACKRABBITS (ALL)	6	qt
W	NM	REPELLENT, RO-PEL	45735-2	RABBITS, COTTONTAIL	6	qt
W	NM	STRYCHNINE MILO (GOPHERS)	56228-19	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	2,152	lb
W	NM	STRYCHNINE MILO (RODENTS)	56228-11	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	2,405	lb
W	NM	STRYCHNINE OATS (FIELD RODENTS)	56228-12	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	120	lb
W	NM	STRYCHNINE OATS (GOPHERS)	56228-20	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	548	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	20	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	NICE, HOUSE	5	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	55	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	RATS, KANGAROO (ALL)	100	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	RATS, NORWAY	20	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE (HOPKINS) RODENT PELLETS	2393-521	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	65	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE OATS (P.DOG)	56228-14	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1,710	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE OATS (P.DOG)	NM-810014	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	220	lb
W	NM	ZINC PHOSPHIDE OATS (P.DOG)	56228-14	PRAIRIE DOGS, WHITE-TAILED	110	lb

* These products were provided by the ADC program for cooperator use.

Table 8. Bird depredation permits recommended by the New Mexico ADC program for issuance by USFWS to cooperators, FY 1993*

Reg	St	Resource Category	Species	Number of Requests for Assistance	Number of Requests Where a Permit Was Not Recommended**	Number of Permits Recommended					Total Number of Permits Recommended
						Harassment	Take	Harassment/ Take	Trap & Relocate	Egg & Nest Destruction	
W		PROPERTY	Crows, (All)***	2 species combined	2 species combined					2 species combined	2
W		PROPERTY	Eagles, Golden								
W		PROPERTY	Hawks, Redtailed								
W		PROPERTY	Passerines, Other								
W		PROPERTY	Pigeons, Feral (Rock Dove)								
W		PROPERTY	Swallows, (Mixed)								
		Total		2	2					2	2

* The ADC program recommends issuance of migratory bird depredation permits by the USFWS where necessary for reduction of depredation.

** Number of requests investigated by ADC that did not result in a recommendation for permit issuance.

*** Total number of incidents was 2, with multiple species involved in each.

Table 9a. Equipment and non-chemical materials loaned for cooperator use by the NEW-MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Type of Equipment/Material	Target Species	Amount Loaned	Unit
W	NM	BALLOONS (ALL)	HAWKS, RED-TAILED	1	Each
W	NM	BALLOONS (ALL)	WOODPECKERS, z-(OTHER)	1	Each
W	NM	ELECTRONIC HARASSMENT DEVICES (ALL)	ELKS (WAPITI)	1	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	BLACKBIRDS, z-(MIXED SPECIES)	3	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	CRANES, SANDHILL	11	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	DOVE, zz-(OTHER)	2	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	ELKS (WAPITI)	2	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	GEESE, CANADA	2	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	LARKS, HORNED	4	Each
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	RAVENS (ALL)	3	Each
W	NM	FLAGS, NON-MYLAR	CRANES, SANDHILL	30	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	CRANES, SANDHILL	1	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	CROWS (ALL)	60	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	DOVE, zz-(OTHER)	1	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	RAVENS (ALL)	1	Each
W	NM	SNARES, FOOT/LEG	BEARS, BLACK	3	Each
W	NM	SNARES, FOOT/LEG	LIONS, MOUNTAIN (COUGAR)	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	BADGERS	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	CATS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	6	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	CHIPMUNKS (ALL)	5	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	DOGS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	5	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	HARES, JACKRABBITS (ALL)	4	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	PIGEONS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	3	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	PORCUPINES	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	1	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RABBITS, COTTONTAIL	5	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RABBITS, z-(OTHER)	1	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RACCOONS	7	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RATS, NORWAY	4	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RATS, PACKRATS/WOODRATS (ALL)	6	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RINGTAILS	1	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SKUNKS, STRIPED	71	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SQUIRRELS, GRAY	1	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	85	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, GOPHER	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	14	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, QUICK-KILL (CONIBEAR)	BEAVERS	2	Each

Table 9b. Irretrievable equipment and non-chemical materials distributed or sold for cooperator use by the NEW MEXICO ADC program, FY 93

Reg	St	Type of Equipment/Material	Target Species	Amount Distributed	Unit
W	NM	EXPLODERS, GAS (ALL)	CRANES, SANDHILL	2	Each
W	NM	GLUE BOARDS	MICE, DEER (ALL)	15	Each
W	NM	GLUE BOARDS	MICE, HOUSE	10	Each
W	NM	GLUE BOARDS	RATS, NORWAY	3	Each
W	NM	GLUE BOARDS	SNAKES, POISONOUS (ALL)	2	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	BLACKBIRDS, z-(MIXED SPECIES)	400	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	COYOTES	25	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	CRANES, SANDHILL	2,403	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	PIGEDNS, FERAL (ROCK DOVE)	40	Each
W	NM	PYROTECHNICS (ALL)	RAVENS (ALL)	600	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	CATS, FERAL/FREE RANGING	11	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RACCOONS	22	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RATS, PACKRATS/WOODRATS (ALL)	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	RINGTAILS	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SKUNKS, STRIPED	27	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SQUIRRELS, GRAY	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	61	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, CAGE	SQUIRRELS, z-(OTHER)	2	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, GOPHER	GOPHERS, POCKET (ALL)	447	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, QUICK-KILL (CONIBEAR)	PRAIRIE DOGS, BLACK-TAILED	7	Each
W	NM	TRAPS, QUICK-KILL (CONIBEAR)	SQUIRRELS, GROUND (ALL)	12	Each

Table 10. Expenditures for conservation of threatened or endangered species (ESA Compliance) by the New Mexico ADC program, FY 1993.

Reg	St	Species Group	Species Protected	Species Status*	ADC Activity (Mark with an X)				Amount Expended				Total Amount Expended
					Section 7 Consultation	Altered Operation	Cooperative Program	Other Activity	Salary	Per Diem	Mileage	Other	
W	NM	BIRD	Eagle, Bald	F/E	X				\$500	\$25			\$525
W	NM	BIRD	Falcon, Aplomado	F/E	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	BIRD	Falcon, Peregrine	F/E	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	BIRD	Goshawk, Northern	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	BIRD	Hawk, Ferruginous	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	BIRD	Hawk, Northern Gray	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	BIRD	Owl, Mexican Spotted	F/T	X				\$300				\$300
													\$0
W	NM	MAMMAL	Chipmunk, Organ Mtn.	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	MAMMAL	Ferrett, Bl. Footed	F/E	X				\$300				\$300
W	NM	Mammal	Fox, Swift	F/**	X				\$375				\$375
W	NM	Mammal	Jack Rabbit, White-side	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	Mammal	Otter, Southwest	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	Mammal	Prairie dog, AZ Bl.-tai	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	Mammal	Rat, Hot Springs Cotton	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	Mammal	Shrew, Arizona	F/**	X				\$25				\$25
W	NM	Mammal	Wolf, Mexican Gray	F/E	X				\$1,000	\$100	\$75		\$1,175
					TOTAL				\$2,750	\$125	\$75		\$2,950

* F/E = Federally listed endangered species
 F/T = Federally listed threatened species
 S/E = State listed endangered species
 S/T = State listed threatened species
 F/** = Federal candidate for listing

Table 11. Harvest and population data of selected species for New Mexico, FY 1993

Reg	St	Species Group	Species	Reported Harvest*		Population			Source of Information
				Total	Year	Estimate	Year	Trend**	
W	NM	Birds	Blackbirds, z-(Mixed)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Declining	U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service
W	NM	Birds	Pigeons, Feral (Rock Dove)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Declining	U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service
W	NM	Mammals	Bears, z-Black (Other)	332	1993-94	4,000	1992	Decreasing	New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Beavers	No Information	N/A	N/A	N/A		New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Bobcats	No Information	N/A	N/A	N/A		New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Coyotes	No Information	N/A	N/A	N/A		New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Lions, Mountain (Cougar)	116	1993-94	N/A	N/A	Stable	New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Raccoons	No Information	N/A	N/A	N/A		New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish
W	NM	Mammals	Skunks, Striped	No Information	N/A	N/A	N/A		New Mexico Dept. Game & Fish

* Does not include data for the ADC program.

** Increasing, Stable, or Decreasing